

Acid Polymerization of Furfural and 5-Hydroxymethylfurfural (HMF). Part II. Kinetic Studies in Furfural Polymerization

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A kinetic study of the rate of polymerization of furfural in presence of orthophosphoric acid as catalyst reveals that rate of polymerization both in air and nitrogen is low and follows a straight line curve initially, but towards the later stages, abrupt changes take place leading to gelation. Experiments have been carried out in air and nitrogen with different percentages of catalysts at 60° and the amount of unchanged furfural has been determined at regular intervals by the standard method.

In a previous communication (Nateson, Ghosh, and Choudhury, this *Journal* 1959, 36, 215), the results of the viscometric studies in the polymerization of furfural with orthophosphoric acid as catalyst have been reported. A kinetic study in the polymerization of furfural with the same catalyst has since been undertaken and the results are presented.

A study of the kinetics of furfural polymerization in presence of mineral acids in aqueous medium has been made by previous workers (Williams and Dunlop, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1948, 40, 239). They found the reaction to be pseudounimolecular and the rate directly proportional to the concentration of hydrogen ion and to the concentration of furfural provided it was in the range of 1-2 per cent. The effect of temperature upon the reaction rate was also studied by them and it was observed that the reaction velocity was accelerated with increase in temperature. From the Arrhenius equation $\frac{d \ln K}{dT} = \frac{E}{RT^2}$, (where K = specific reaction rate, E = energy of activation, R = molar gas constant, and T = temperature), they also calculated the value of the energy of activation and found it to be 20 k cal./mole.

While Williams and Dunlop (*loc. cit.*) were able to derive a mathematical expression, which would permit calculation of the rate of polymerization of furfural (1-2%) with mineral acids in aqueous medium, the present work was undertaken with the object of determining the rate of polymerization of 100% furfural with orthophosphoric acid as catalyst. Orthophosphoric acid was selected as catalyst due to its mild acidic nature compared to the mineral acids, and it permitted the polymer from furfural formed during reaction to be present in linear soluble stage during the progress of the reaction. With mineral acids, even with very low concentration, furfural polymers formed even during the initial stages became completely cross-linked preventing thereby further study of the kinetics.

EXPERIMENTAL

A sample of pure furfural (100 g.) (colorless, b.p. 161.7°), freshly distilled under high vacuum from the commercial product, was treated with orthophosphoric acid (from 10g. to 30g.) of sp. gr. 1.75 as catalyst in a three-necked flask (250 c.c.). It was then well stirred and kept in a thermostatic bath at 60±0.1°. The sample was continuously stirred with a

mechanical stirrer. Some of the initial studies were made under ordinary atmospheric conditions and some of those later under nitrogen.

Analysis (Volumetric).—The method of Hughes and Acree (*Ind. Eng. Chem., Anal. Ed.*, 1936, 6, 292) was followed by us for the quick and accurate estimation of furfural during the process.

About 0.5-g. of the sample was weighed out from the reaction vessel at regular intervals of time, and then diluted to 500 c.c. with distilled water in a volumetric flask. The monomer remained in solution, and if at any time any precipitate formed, it was allowed to settle.

This prepared solution (25 c.c.) was then transferred to a specially prepared titration flask (500 c.c.) containing 200 c. c. of 3% HCl (A.R.). The flask contained two side arms (100 c.c.) at right angles to each other. 1*N*-KBrO₃-KBr solution (25c.c.; 50 g. KBr/litre) and 10 c. c. of 10% KI solution were kept in the two side arms of the titration flask. (The use of this flask is to eliminate the possibility of loss of bromine). The flask was then placed in an ice bath for some time till the temperature of the solution was below 2°. Then the KBrO₃-KBr solution was added to it, and kept for 3 minutes for the completion of the reaction. KI solution was then added and the excess I₂ liberated was titrated with 0.1*N* thiosulphate solution using starch as indicator. Blank experiment was also performed with the same volume of reagents and the volume of thiosulphate solution for unchanged furfural was then calculated.

Thiosulphate solution (0.1*N*, 1 c.c.) = 0.0048g. of furfural.

From the above relation, the percentage of unchanged furfural was calculated. The results are presented in Tables I and II.

TABLE I

Polymerization under atmospheric conditions at 60±0.1°.

No.	Time of polymerization (hr.).	Amount of furfural (%).					
		(a).		(b).		(c).	
		Unchanged.	Consumed (calc.).	Unchanged.	Consumed (calc.).	Unchanged.	Consumed (calc.).
1.	0	100.00	0.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	0.00
2.	20	99.32	0.68	98.85	1.15	98.10	1.90
3.	44	97.85	2.15	97.35	2.65	92.75	7.25
4.	68	95.05	4.95	94.32	5.68	88.95	11.05
5.	92	93.25	6.75	91.40	8.60	88.43	11.57
6.	116	92.76	7.24	92.38	7.62	85.55	14.45
7.	140	91.81	8.19	89.42	10.58		
8.	164	91.99	8.01	88.56	11.44		
9.	188	90.52	9.48				
10.	212	87.58	12.42	85.89	14.17		
11.	236	88.45	11.55	83.65	16.35		
12.	260	91.75	8.25	86.80	13.20		
13.	284	85.68	14.32				
14.	308	79.70	20.30				
15.	332	80.32	19.68				

Catalyst H₃ PO₄: per 100g. furfural. (a) 7½g., (b) 15 g., (c) 30 g.

TABLE II
Polymerization under nitrogen at $60 \pm 0.1^\circ$.

No.	Time of Polymerization (hr.)	(a).		No.	Time of Polymerization (hr.)	(b).	
		Amount of Unchanged.	Amount of furfural (%) Consumed (calc.).			Amount of Unchanged.	Amount of furfural (%) Consumed (calc.).
1.	0	100.00	0.00	1.	0	100.00	0.00
2.	24	99.09	0.97	2.	22	99.00	1.00
3.	48	98.10	1.90	3.	46	98.15	1.85
4.	72	99.00	1.00	4.	70	98.00	2.00
5.	96	97.50	2.50	5.	94	95.70	4.30
6.	120	..	..	6.	116	..	..
7.	144	95.95	4.05	7.	121	..	..
8.	192	92.20	7.80	8.	144	93.20	6.80
9.	216	91.10	8.90	9.	168	92.50	7.50
10.	240	90.45	9.55	10.	189	92.08	7.92
11.	264	87.33	12.67	11.	213	92.83	7.17
12.	288	84.86	15.14	12.	237	91.89	8.11
				13.	261	90.44	9.56

Catalyst H_3PO_4 : per 100 g. Furfural. (a) 10 g., (b) 15 g.

The percentage of furfural consumed has been plotted against time and a smooth curve has been drawn which initially resembles a straight line, but at later stages shows a sudden deviation in the upward direction probably due to gelation.

DISCUSSION

It is evident from the data in Tables I and II that the conversion of furfural monomer into furfural polymer in air as well as in nitrogen was very small even after a prolonged period of reaction. When the percentage of polymer formation was plotted against time of polymerization, straight line curves in each case were obtained (curves 1, 2 and 3.) The data in the later stages in the curves did not always lie on the straight line. It was also

FIG. 1.

Curves 1-3 refer respectively to 7.5g. H_3PO_4 , 15g. H_3PO_4 and 30g. H_3PO_4 per 100 g. furfural.

observed from the curves that the rate of reaction depended completely upon the concentrations of the catalyst (temperature remaining constant). After 100 hrs. of reaction with 7.5% catalyst concentration 5% furfural polymerized, whereas with 30% catalyst only 14% furfural polymerized under the same atmospheric conditions.

FIG. 2. Curves 1 and 2 refer respectively to 10g. H₃PO₄+100g. furfural and 15g. H₃PO₄+100g. furfural.

In Table II data collected under nitrogen have been presented. It was observed that the polymerization rate was very small in this case also and only a small fraction of the monomer (10-15%) polymerized even after 300 hrs. A curve (Fig. 2) similar to that obtained earlier in presence of air (Fig. 1) was obtained by plotting the percentage of polymer formation against time of polymerization. The dependence of the rate of reaction upon concentration of the catalyst was observed here also.

From the analysis of data, thus far collected, it is apparent that results more or less similar in nature are obtained with different percentages of catalyst both under atmospheric conditions as well as under nitrogen. The reaction appeared to be pseudo-unimolecular in nature, but it did not obey the same order during the later stages. The specific reaction rate has been calculated to be of the order of 10^{-5} to 10^{-7} sec⁻¹ depending on the concentration of the catalyst (assuming the first order kinetic equation to be valid in each case).

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